

POLICE ADMINISTRATION IN NAXAL AFFECTED AREAS OF MAHARASHTRA

Dharmendra Turkar,
RTM Nagpur University, Nagpur

Abstract :-

The movement of Naxalism started from small village of Naxalbari has transformed into an extensive form. The movement which was started for the rights of farmers and weaker sections has now been a big challenge for the nation. Naxalism is the biggest threat to Internal Security of the nation, mentioned Prime Minister himself based on the report of intelligence agencies and that underlines the importance of the issue. Presently, country's security system has got badly affected due to Naxal acts. This has put a big question mark on the internal security of the nation. Naxalism is transformed into a vast movement and according to the report of Institute of Conflict Management it has been spread in the 14 states and 165 districts.

Local police on state level and Central Reserve Police Force on central level are working, to stop the increasing impact of Naxal movement. CRPF is working in tune with local police in concern Naxal affected area. Law and order situation are handled in Naxal affected area through local police, CRPF, SRPF and other intelligence agencies. The role of police administration is major in this crisis handling.

Keywords: - Police Administration, Naxal, Naxal Affected Areas, Law and Order

Introduction: -

Police Administration- Role in law and order situation

Police administration is an important part of district administration. Police administration has important responsibility to establish law and order situation in country and state. According to subject list distribution in the constitution, police administration is included in the 66 subjects of state list. As this subject is included in the state list, every state has separate police administration.

The major base of Indian police administration is Madras Police Act-1861. After independence, Indian constitution made some changes in the 1861 act to create CRPF act

1949 and formed Central Reserve Police force. All state police forces and SRPFs have been formed in each state on the same basis of this act.

Structure of State Police force

State police administration works under the control of State Home Ministry. Home ministry has two-layer structure. One is political layer another is administrative level. On political level, a minister namely Home Minister is appointed. He is a non-permanent or non-governmental head of the department. There are one or two ministers of state to help Home Minister. These assistant ministers are assigned with the responsibilities of specific departments or sections of the work.

On administrative level, there is a secretariat of this ministry where there is a chief officer to handle the work who is called as home secretary. He or she is the experience and senior office in the administrative services. Below him, there is an administrative chief to handle the administrative work. He is also identified as Permanent Chief and called as Director General of Police. He has got his headquarter at Mumbai and is appointed by state government. He is responsible for all aspects related to police administration in the state. He has to travel across the state to ensure law and order. He is assisted by additional Director General of Police, one Special Inspector General for administrative work, two Deputy IGs and three assistant IGs of Superintendent level. All these seven officers look after the work from Police Headquarter.

Administrative structure of Home Ministry (Police administration)

Home Ministry

Home Minister, Home Secretary

Director General of Police

Additional Director General of Police

Special Inspector General of Police

Deputy Inspector General of Police

Assistant Inspector General of Police

Commissioner of Police (For Metros)

Additional Commissioner

Deputy Police Commissioner

Police Inspector

Assistant Police Inspector

Police Sub Inspector

Head Constable

Peon

Deputy Inspector General of Police (For Regional departments)

Superintendent of Police

Assistant Superintendent of Police

Deputy Superintendent

Circle Police Inspector

Police Inspector

Assistant Police Inspector

Sub Inspector

Head Constable

Peon

Elements of Police administration

There are seven official elements of Police Administration in which work of police department has been divided. Maintaining law and order is the main work of Police administration and following departments have been formed to work and work division has been done accordingly.

1. Crime Investigation department
2. Motor Transport department
3. Railway Police
4. Traffic Police
5. Wireless Police
6. Reserve Police
7. Police Prosecutors

Police administration is working effectively in all seven departments. Due to increase in the population separate Police Commissioner offices have been formed in Maharashtra at Mumbai, Pune, Thane, Nagpur, Amravati and Aurangabad and Police Commissioners have been appointed at these places. All these are experienced officers in Indian Police Service. Apart from these cities entire police administration is divided into seven regional departments as given below.

Table No 5.2

Table of Police administration divided into seven regional departments.

SN	Region	Included districts
1	Thane	Thane Rural, Raigad, Ratnagiri, Sindhudurg
2	Nashik	Nashik, Ahmednagar, Jalgaon, Dhule and Nandurbar
3	Kolhapur	Kolhapur, Pune Rural, Satara, Sangli and Solapur
4	Aurangabad	Aurangabad Rural, Jalna, Beed and Usmanabad
5	Nanded	Nanded, Latur, Parabhani and Hingoli
6	Amravati	Amravati, Yavatmal, Washim, Akola, Buldana
7	Nagpur	Nagpur rural, Chandrapur, Wardha, Bhandara, Gondia, Gadchiroli.

Table Reference: Salgare V.K. district administration, Aurangabad, Kailas Publication, Page No.

Every Regional department is under Deputy IG level officer who is a bridge between Director General of Police and all District Superintendent of Police. This officer is responsible for all elements in regional areas. On regional level, the work is divided into different cells. Deputy Police Inspector General provided information in specific region to DIG. Below him appointed are Superintendent of Police (IPS) on all district levels. Below him there are Assistant SPs or DYSPs, SDPOs who are from Maharashtra Police Service. For every police station, there are Police Inspectors who are assisted by Police Sub Inspectors. Below officer levels there are head constables and constables to handle the law and order situation.

Police administration in Naxal affected area

Police administration has important responsibility of maintaining law and order and the general public life intact. Due to activeness of police administration, public in general gets assurance of life and property safety. Police administration is the backbone of law and it has responsibility of implementation of law through people and establishing the rule of law. It also handles the responsibility of coordination between government and people and maintaining law and order in the district.

Prohibitory measures of Police administration

Naxal movement was started with a specific motive . In the beginning, Jamindars and

rich people were enemies of Naxals. They used the Mao's principle of armed revolution. Robbing riches using arms and distributing their wealth amongst poors was the working style in earlier period. Due to armed clashes, administration felt the threat to law and order and hence police had to start taking action against Naxals. Maintaining law and order is the basic task of police department and hence it become obvious for police to restrict the activities of Naxals. For the very purpose of Naxal eradication police department is using 'Unlawful activities prevention act 2004'.

As Naxals opt for armed and violent methods, police is also forced to take armed action them. Police fight on two fronts for eradication of Naxals from Naxal affected area.

A. Armed Action against Naxals

B. Awareness amongst people.

On the first front police are taking armed action against Naxals to stop them and doing various operations for that. Police are trying to give befitting reply to stop Naxals. On the second front, Police organize various programmes to create awareness among people by telling them the original philosophy of Naxals, providing information about their violent actions, how they are creating obstacles in the development work and other such things. By providing all such information, police is trying to take away people from Naxal influence and trying to bring in them in mainstream of the society. Police administration is fighting Naxals on these both fronts and trying to curb the movement and its actions.

Armed struggle for Naxal eradication

Police administration takes armed action to stop Naxal acts and for their eradication. As Naxals are involved in the armed struggle, police also need to take armed action against them. Various different operation and search operations are implemented. If Naxals are encountered, instructions are given to them for surrender. But most of the time they start firing instead of surrendering and that makes it compulsory for police to retaliate and fire. Even in these police try to capture Naxals alive or in wounded conditions.

Police rely on information while working in Naxal affected areas. Police have informers in all areas who give intelligence, they work on local level and inform police. The information is reliable as it is given by localites and on that basis police makes their action plan which is primarily of four types.

1. Long Distance Patrolling:

Police use this method in Naxal affected areas for the search of Naxals. In this operation, police squad undertake continuous 48 hours search operation in remote areas. They need

to walk in forests carrying arms and necessary things. Targets in such operations are predecided. Police take shelter and food in nearby villages. These kind of patrolling helps to reduce impact of Naxals in far remote areas. This helps to have communication with people in tribal areas and take government's people welfare policy upto the people. This also helps to curb the Naxal movement and people also get to know that Police are serious in taking action against Naxals.

2. Short distance patrolling:

Police conduct Naxal search operation on feet in a particular area from morning to evening and this is called as Short distance patrolling. In this, police team do patrolling in the morning carrying their food and arms in the affected area. A squad of 5 to 10 police cops do search operation on feet in search of Naxals. They also take review of villages and problems of villagers during this patrolling. They try to assure people to provide security against Naxals through such patrolling. Such patrolling efforts affect the work of Naxals and force them to migrate more often. This reduce their influence in the region. If encountered, police have all the rights to take necessary action required according to conditions.

3. Road opening:

Naxals target roads to hamper development works in the affected areas which creates problems for the transport and traffic. Hence, Anti Naxal squad of police department takes up the work of road opening. To provide all protection to Border Road Organization while working, to ensure that there are no explosives planted before starting the work. These road openings are worked out before start of the work in the morning. Patrolling is done to search explosives on both sides of the roads so as to avoid disruption of traffic on main roads. This helps to provide security to prominent roads in Naxal affected area.

4. Ambush:

On the basis of secret information, police take hide in suspected area and cordon off the spot. When Naxals reach there, they are asked to surrender but if they start firing, befitting reply is also given by police. This is called as Ambush.

Executing such actions, police department tries to control Naxals. As the aim is to totally uproot Naxal movement, police take all the necessary armed action to achieve their target. Police also takes efforts to curb the armed terror of Naxals by using arms only. But only armed fights may bring one sided and half successes, police need to take efforts on create

awareness among people in Naxal affected areas where Naxals instigate locals against administration and join them in the movement.

Police department carry out two works of armed resistance and awareness in people simultaneously. Due to armed search operations, many Naxals have been arrested and many arms and other material have been seized from them.

B Public awareness

Police with armed actions and operations create its influence on the area with the aim of Naxal eradication. Department is also expected to do some social works in the region.

Police department works to create awareness among people in the region and shape their mindset to work against Naxal movement and in support of police department. Efforts are taken to reveal the real facet of Naxal movement, need to prohibition of extremists and to give information about the development works carried out by the government. For the very purpose, police department undertakes public contact and awareness programme which include following things.

1. Village Visit
2. School Visit
3. Gramasabha Visit
4. Public awareness programmes
5. Community reconciliation camps
6. Shanti Yatra
7. Surrender scheme of government

1. Village visit:

Thought Naxals stay in deep jungles, they rely very much on the villages inside forests. They hide behind villages as their needs to survive can only be satisfied through villages. People help them as they come under the impression of their philosophy and consider that Naxals are working for their benefit. Some other help them due to threat to life. Police visit to such villages and communicate with villagers. They purposefully visit villages during long and short distance patrolling, listen to problems of villagers and take reviews of problems related to roads, water, electricity, communication, schools, Anganwadi, medical and veterinary as well as revenue department problems. Superintendent of police department send all those problems and complaints to concern departments and efforts are taken to solve problems as fast as possible. As Naxals always point out lack of development in the region and instigate people, administration tries to complete

development works as much as possible. Police also try to stop people from joining Naxal movement, inform people about actions of Naxals and tries to convince people that police are their real friends while Naxals are their enemy.

2. School visit

During visit to Naxal affected areas, police also visit local schools. Students are informed about how Naxalism is a threat for the country and for the development. The motive behind this is that these students should pursue their parents from joining the movement.

3. Gramsabha visits:

During Village visits, Police take information about the date of Gram Sabha and police officials and employees attend those meetings. They appeal people to stay away from Naxal movement and help police administration. Police also ask Gram Sabhas to prohibit Naxals from entering villages and also inform about the prize of Rs. 2 lakh for villages. Police takes efforts to make people understand that they should not cooperate with Naxals by any means and should stop their entry in the village. Police is quite aware that Naxal eradication is totally impossible without co-operation from local people.

4. Awareness camps:

Police on one hand fight with arms against Naxals and on the other hand create awareness among people to appeal them about staying away from Naxal movement and help the government. Police is well aware that they cannot act effectively against Naxals without co-operation from local people. Hence, they organize public awareness camps from 5 to 7 villages. Superintendent of Police and department heads of different government departments attend these camps. People raise their grievances about various works and department heads try to solve them. Such camps helps people to put their problems to government departments and helps administration to understand problems of people. Grievances include mostly those related to water, roads, electricity, education, communication, revenue., transport and medical. Actually, such problems should be solved by local representatives of people and the administration but people's representatives do not pay required attention for such works which creates unrest among people in Naxal affected areas and Naxal groups reap benefit of this situation.

Public awareness camps help to solve such problems. These helps to remove fear of Naxals among people and they start opposing to co-operate Naxals. Police invite local important persons as well as heads of castes and tribes in camps. They communicate with people in local language and ask them to stay away from Naxal movement as well as to

not to help them in any way. This create atmosphere in the region against Naxals and makes it difficult for them to work in the region. Police department, in 2006 had organized such 19 camps in Gondia district.

5.Community Reconciliation camps:

To avoid any communal tension among people of different castes and religions living in Naxal affected areas, to maintain social harmony , to avoid any law and order situation and to stop Naxals from taking benefit of it, police department organizes community reconciliation camps.

Police department contact heads of all castes and religions, representatives of all religious organizations and create awareness about social and religious harmony. Naxals largely concentrate on tribal people in the region. Hence, to avoid disconnect of tribals with other backward classes, to avoid any tension among them and to unite all for fighting against Naxals, police department tries to bring together heads of all castes and religions through these camps. These heads appeal people to stay away from naxals and to cooperate administration. As appeals are made by prominent people in the community, it creates major impact on people and helps to create awareness among people and also to keep them away from Naxal movement.

6.Shanti Yatra:

A fear always prevail in Naxal affected areas due to actions of Naxals. Due to their violent methods, people hardly dare to act against Naxalists and areas get affected due to Naxal activities. Shanti Yatras are organized in such area in which heads of all castes, religions and sects, prominent people in the society, common people, school children and women participate. Police officials attend such Shanti Yatras and appeal people to cooperate the government against Naxals.

Surrender scheme of the government:

Considering the increasing influence of Naxal movement, police administration take efforts to suppress it. They inform about surrender scheme through public awareness activities and appeal Naxals to live with pride and leaving armed and violent path of life. To facilitate this government is trying to appeal Naxals to participate in the process of development instead of fighting against the government.

Police administration creates background to facilitate surrender of Naxalists while district administration implements their rehabilitation work. Police department through various

programmes inform about the facilities and benefits for surrendered Naxals. Department also provide them assurance of security and rehabilitation after surrendering.

Surrendered Naxalists are thoroughly inquired and inquiry is also done about their responses and references of events. They are classified according to weapon he or she was carrying and the post he or she was holding at the time of surrender and their grade is decided accordingly for monetary benefits as well as for rehabilitation. Police administration takes follow up and implementation of surrender scheme. Gondiya police is also trying hard for this.

After complete inquiry and cross checking of surrendered Naxals, they are given government monetary benefits, residential benefits, education for children, help to start business, agricultural lands and other such benefits for proper rehabilitation. Considering threat to their life, security is also provided to them. They are also rehabilitated in other areas depending on the situation. District police administration is confident that number Naxals surrendering will surely increase due to facilities, security and opportunities of rehabilitation provided to them.

Through all these efforts, police administration appeals Naxals to move away from path of violence, surrender and live with self esteem and participate in the mainstream life of the society. It appeals people to stay from the movement by organizing public awareness campaigns, community gatherings and Shanti Yatras. Appeals of surrenders made by community heads have proved more beneficial.

Through such activities, publicity of government's surrender scheme is done. Pamphlets are displayed and distributed in villages about this and information about benefits after surrender is also given through it.

In this way, police administration is working in Naxal affected area for maintaining law and order situation. Due to cooperation from local people, Police could work effectively in this region. Due to armed threat of Naxals, earlier locals could not dare to go against them but now they are tired of constant violent agitations, killings of locals and getting aware through awareness campaigns of police department. Locals who till now used to support Naxals in the name of development and oppose the government are now co-operating with the administration. Gramsabhas are passing resolution about denying entries to Naxals in villages. Till now, following villages in Gondiya district have denied entry to Naxals.

Due to denial for entry in villagers, work of Naxals has got affected. Stagnation in

agitation or more violence in agitations are witnesses. Villages who have passed such resolutions and implementing it are provided development fund of Rs 2 lakh by the government. This has created positive approach among people for the government. At the same time, such villages face threat from Naxals and many times Village heads or others are beaten or killed by Naxals. They are spread false information about monetary benefits by government and create unrest among people.

Reference:

Chaturvedi S.K. (1988): Police and Emerging Challenges, Delhi: B.R. Publishing.

Mathur Krishna Mohan (1987): Administration of Police Training in India, Delhi: Gyan Publishing House.

Record of Gondia District Police.

The Indian Police Journal-Vol-LV.No1 (Jan-March 2009)- Bureau of Police Research & Development, Ministry of Home Affairs, Govt. of India New Delhi.110020.